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COLLIDER PERFORMANCE, BEAM OPTICS AND DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS BASELINE

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Abstract:

We report a preliminary FCC-ee baseline layout for optimised placement, comment on the associated beam optics and the expected performance and highlight some of the issues that remain to be addressed.

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1. DESIGN APPROACH

1.1. LAYOUT AND OPTICS

The FCC-ee electron-positron collider is conceived as a double-ring collider with a full-energy top-up booster ring. The Conceptual Design Report (CDR), published in 2019 [1], described the baseline FCC-ee design with a circumference of 97.75 km, 12 surface sites, and two collision points. In 2021, a careful revision of constraints has resulted in an optimised placement of much lower risk, with a circumference of 91.2 km and only 8 surface sites, and which would be compatible with either 2 or 4 collision points – see Figure 1. Consequently, adapting the CDR design and re-optimisation of the machine parameters are underway, taking into account not only the new placement, but also the possibly larger number of interaction points, and the mitigation of complex “combined” effects, e/g. the interplay of transverse and longitudinal impedance with the beam-beam interaction. The newest collider layout is chosen with eight surface sites and with a perfect superperiodicity of four, so that it can accommodate either two or four Interaction Points (IPs) with experiments. Two or more other straights house the radiofrequency (RF) cavities. The strength of the arc magnets is tapered to match the local energy. An asymmetric interaction region (IR) layout limits the photon energies of the synchrotron radiation (SR) emitted by the incoming beams over the last ~500 m upstream of the IP towards detectors, and, at the same time, generates the large crossing angle [2].

A common use of the RF systems for both beams is planned at the highest-energy working point (ttbar), where each beam comprises only a few tens of bunches, to minimise the cost of construction. Key parameters for both colliders are compiled in Table 1, which will be updated as the further machine optimisation advances.

Figure 1: Optimised FCC-ee placement with eight surface sites, a lattice super-periodicity of 4, and either two or four interaction points (J. Gutleber, V. Mertens).

1.2. OPERATIONAL CONCEPTS

Two important operational ingredients are “bootstrapping injection” and top-up injection [3]. Alternating re-injection to “top up” the circulating electron and positron bunches maintains approximately constant beam current and luminosity, so that the average luminosity of FCC-ee approaches the peak luminosity.

Intensities of colliding bunches must be kept equal to within a few percent to avoid a beam-beam flip-flop effect, where one bunch would blow up and the opposite bunch shrink, resulting in an unrecoverable situation. For the same reason, when filling the machine from zero, a bootstrapping injection process is foreseen, with alternating injections into either of the two collider rings, avoiding large charge imbalances [3].

At the FCC-ee, highly precise energy calibration using resonant depolarisation at c.m. energies of 91 and 160 GeV, with wiggler-polarised pilot bunches, and roughly 10^5 times higher luminosity than LEP, will allow measuring the masses of the Z and W bosons, as well as the width of the Z, with 20-50x improved precision, rendering the FCC-ee an exceptional electroweak factory [4].

1.3. OPTIONAL RUNNING MODE

In addition to the 4 baseline running modes shown in Table 1, another optional operation mode is presently under investigation for FCC-ee, namely the direct s-channel Higgs production, $e^+e^- \rightarrow H$, at a centre-of-mass energy of 125 GeV. Here, a monochromatization scheme should reduce the effective collision energy spread so as to become comparable to the width of the Higgs [5]. This type of operation would provide experimental access to the electron Yukawa coupling.

2. EXPECTED PERFORMANCE

2.1. PARAMETER CONSTRAINTS

The FCC-ee parameter optimisation takes into account beam-beam effects (coherent beam-beam instability [6], flip-flop effects, beamstrahlung, etc.), impedance and single-beam collective effects, and the interplay of impedance and beam-beam interaction. The beam optics, including errors and optics corrections, must provide adequate dynamic aperture, including off-momentum dynamic aperture. The off-momentum dynamic aperture limits the beam lifetime in the ZH and $t\bar{t}$ running modes due to beamstrahlung and radiative Bhabha scattering.

2.2. PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

The performance requirements were specified in a submission to the European Strategy Process 2018 [7]: “To provide relevant sensitivity to new physics, the FCC-ee must deliver integrated luminosities at centre-of-mass energies from around the Z pole to above the top-pair threshold, such that the statistical precision of a complete set of electroweak and Higgs observables improves by one to two orders of magnitude. The data samples needed to achieve this goal correspond to:

1. An integrated luminosity of **30 ab^{-1} at $\sqrt{s} \sim 88$ and at 94 GeV** for the direct measurement of the electromagnetic coupling constant at the Z mass scale. These data are also useful for the determination of the Z total width.
2. An integrated luminosity of **$\sim 100 \text{ab}^{-1}$ at the Z pole** for the measurement of the effective weak mixing angle and for the search for and the study of rare Z decays. These data are also important for the determination of the Z mass and of the strong coupling constant at the Z mass scale.
3. An integrated luminosity of **10 ab^{-1} around the WW threshold**, for the measurement of the W mass and width, evenly shared between $\sqrt{s} \sim 157.5$ and 162.5 GeV. These data also provide the number of neutrino species and an independent measurement of the strong coupling constant.
4. An integrated luminosity of **5 ab^{-1} at $\sqrt{s} = 240$ GeV** for an absolute measurement of the Higgs boson couplings and decay width, that breaks the model-dependence inherent to hadron colliders.
5. An integrated luminosity of **$\sim 0.2 \text{ab}^{-1}$ in a 5-GeV-wide window around the top-pair threshold**, typically shared among eight points from ~ 340 to ~ 345 GeV for the measurement of the top-quark mass and width.
6. An integrated luminosity of **1.5 ab^{-1} above the top-pair threshold, $\sqrt{s} \sim 365$ GeV**, optimal for the measurement of the top electroweak couplings. These data provide a threefold improvement of the Higgs boson width accuracy with respect to the 240 GeV data, and allow for the first 3σ evidence of the Higgs self-coupling.”

2.3. PARAMETER TABLES

A preliminary table with key FCC-ee parameters for the case of four IPs is shown in Table 1 below. In the CDR operation at the Z and W assumed a 60°/60° phase advance per arc cell. The mitigation of the combined impedance and beam-beam effects requires a larger momentum compaction factor than in the CDR. This has resulted in a “long” 90° cell, of twice the cell length used for the H and ttbar operation. Comparing Table 1 with the CDR [1], we note:

- The beam lifetime at the H is 40% shorter than in the CDR, namely about 7 minutes instead of 12 minutes. This is due to the reduction of the damping between two consecutive IPs.
- The RF voltage at the W pair threshold, with the long 90°/90° lattice, is increased by 33% compared with the CDR (from 0.75 to 1.0 GV), to obtain a synchrotron tune sufficiently high for energy calibration via resonant depolarisation.
- The drop of luminosity from the CDR value is largest for the W, from 28 to $17 \times 10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, due to the larger emittance with the long 90°/90° cell (2.17 nm versus 0.84 nm), as somewhat expected.

The beam parameters, in particular the emittances, bunch length, lifetime, and luminosity need to be validated in strong-strong beam-beam simulations and in weak-strong simulations including errors and optics corrections. A similar parameter for the case of two IPs is presented in Table 2. The luminosity values per IP are similar to the previous case, or slightly higher. Therefore, the beam lifetime due to radiative Bhabha scattering (inversely proportional to the total luminosity) is about factor two higher, which allows a more aggressive choice for the beamstrahlung-induced lifetime in $t\bar{t}$ operation.

Table 1: Preliminary design parameters for FCC-ee for four different modes of operation, considering a machine with four interaction points (Katsunobu Oide).

Beam energy	[GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Layout		PA31-1.0			
# of IPs		4			
Circumference	[km]	91.180			
Bending radius of arc dipole	[km]	9.935			
Energy loss / turn	[GeV]	0.0391	0.370	1.869	10.0
SR power / beam	[MW]	50			
Beam current	[mA]	1400	135	26.7	5.00
Bunches / beam		8800	1120	336	42
Bunch population	[10^{11}]	2.76	2.29	1.51	2.26
Horizontal emittance ε_x	[nm]	0.71	2.17	0.64	1.49
Vertical emittance ε_y	[pm]	1.42	4.34	1.29	2.98
Arc cell		Long 90/90		90/90	
Momentum compaction α_p	[10^{-6}]	28.5		7.33	
Arc sextupole families		75		146	
$\beta_{x/y}^*$	[mm]	150 / 0.8	200 / 1.0	300 / 1.0	1000 / 1.6
Transverse tunes/IP $Q_{x/y}$		55.543 / 55.600		100.543 / 99.600	
Energy spread (SR/BS) σ_δ	[%]	0.039 / 0.138	0.069 / 0.136	0.103 / 0.184	0.157 / 0.238
Bunch length (SR/BS) σ_z	[mm]	4.32 / 15.2	3.55 / 7.02	2.50 / 4.45	1.67 / 2.54
RF voltage 400/800 MHz	[GV]	0.120 / 0	1.0 / 0	2.48 / 0	4.0 / 7.67
Synchrotron tune Q_s		0.0370	0.0800	0.0438	0.0890
Long. damping time	[turns]	1170	216	64.5	18.5
RF acceptance	[%]	1.6	3.3	2.3	3.7
Energy acceptance (DA)	[%]	± 1.3	± 1.3	± 1.7	-2.8 +2.5
Beam-beam ξ_x/ξ_y^a		0.0040 / 0.159	0.011 / 0.111	0.0187 / 0.129	0.096 / 0.138
Luminosity / IP	[$10^{34}/\text{cm}^2\text{s}$]	181	17.3	7.2	1.25
Lifetime (q + BS)	[sec]		–	1142	2770
Lifetime (lum)	[sec]	1136	1197	604	743

^aincl. hourglass.

Table 2: Preliminary design parameters for FCC-ee for four different modes of operation, considering a machine with two interaction points (Katsunobu Oide).

Beam energy	[GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Layout		PA31-1.0			
# of IPs		2			
Circumference	[km]	91.180			
Bending radius of arc dipole	[km]	9.935			
Energy loss / turn	[GeV]	0.0391	0.370	1.869	10.0
SR power / beam	[MW]	50			
Beam current	[mA]	1400	135	26.7	5.00
Bunches / beam		11600	1120	380	44
Bunch population	[10 ¹¹]	2.09	2.29	1.33	2.16
Horizontal emittance ε_x	[nm]	0.71	2.17	0.64	1.49
Vertical emittance ε_y	[pm]	1.42	4.34	1.29	2.98
Arc cell		Long 90/90		90/90	
Momentum compaction α_p	[10 ⁻⁶]	28.5		7.33	
Arc sextupole families		150		146	
$\beta_{x/y}^*$	[mm]	150 / 0.8	200 / 1.0	300 / 1.0	1000 / 1.6
Transverse tunes/IP $Q_{x/y}$		110.543 / 110.600		200.543 / 198.600	
Energy spread (SR/BS) σ_δ	[%]	0.039 / 0.103	0.069 / 0.121	0.103 / 0.155	0.157 / 0.203
Bunch length (SR/BS) σ_z	[mm]	4.35 / 11.4	3.55 / 7.02	2.50 / 3.75	1.67 / 2.16
RF voltage 400/800 MHz	[GV]	0.120 / 0	1.0 / 0	2.48 / 0	4.0 / 7.67
Synchrotron tune Q_s		0.0370	0.0800	0.0438	0.0890
Long. damping time	[turns]	1170	216	64.5	18.5
RF acceptance	[%]	1.6	3.3	2.3	3.7
Energy acceptance (DA)	[%]	± 1.3	± 1.3	± 1.7	-2.8 +2.5
Beam-beam ξ_x/ξ_y^a		0.0054 / 0.160	0.014 / 0.125	0.0227 / 0.134	0.106 / 0.139
Luminosity / IP	[10 ³⁴ /cm ² s]	181	19.5	7.48	1.31
Lifetime (q + BS)	[sec]	-		1317	1412
Lifetime (lum)	[sec]	2281	2130	1159	1417

^aincl. hourglass.

The parameter tables are also posted at: https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/FCCeeParameters_PA31-1_0. These tables will be continually updated as the design optimisation progresses. Even without taking machine errors into account, the parameters of Tables 1 and 2 require further optimization for the number of bunches at each energy, for instance. Detailed studies on the effects of lattice errors and optics corrections, and also of the impact of the transverse impedance, have just started, and may lead to additional parameter adjustments.

2.4. RUN PLAN

The proposed run schedule and total integrated luminosity evolution for each of the four base modes of operation according to the CDR [1] are illustrated in Figure 2. Note that a one-year shutdown is foreseen between the Higgs (HZ) production run and top-quark operation. This year allows for the rearrangement of the RF cavity sections, for separate beamlines to a shared beam line, and for the installation of a significant number of additional cavities. All the goals of the FCC-ee baseline program shall be achieved within 15 years of operation.

Figure 2: FCC-ee operation model showing the integrated luminosity in ab^{-1} , accumulated as a function of time in years at the Z pole (black), the WW threshold (blue), the Higgs factory (red) and the top-pair threshold (green). The hatched area indicates the shutdown time to prepare for the highest energy runs; reproduced from [1] and [7].

3. REFERENCES

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